

Deliverable No. 13.2
Communication Plan

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R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	
DMP: Data Management Plan	
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc	

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1 INTRODUCTION AND SUMMARY

QUASAR is a 4-years project funded by Horizon Europe (2023-2027)

QUASAR is committed to sustainability, focusing on recycling end-of-life PV modules and promoting a circular economy in the solar industry. With 19 partners from 9 countries, we're collaborating to advance circular practices and drive photovoltaic solar energy into the future. Funded by the European Union's Horizon Program, QUASAR is paving the way for a competitive PV solar industry.

The external communication and dissemination plan aims at precisising the type of activities and variety of audiences to maximize the promotion of QUASAR and its impact.

This plan identifies the information needs of the specific project stakeholders and determines channels for tailored, target-specific communications and dissemination activities. In accordance with the glossary of terms “communication” and “dissemination” available on the EC Europa Website, this plan contains:

- Appropriate means to publicly disclose the results - other than protecting or exploiting them. e.g., scientific publications (dissemination).
- Strategic and targeted measures to communicate about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange (communication).

Thus, the external communication and dissemination plan consists of a strategic plan for the use and dissemination of results of the QUASAR project. Results refer to any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature. It is structured in two parts:

- Description of the dissemination procedure
- Presentation of the communication plan

This plan ensures that QUASAR partners will provide the knowledge gained during the project's lifetime in the right format, at the right time and with the right impact.

By doing this, we are striving for enhancing the awareness and comprehension of the processes involved in recycling PV systems and based on this knowledge, to develop and implement more effective and sustainable solutions for decommissioning solar panels. This knowledge can then be applied to work towards scaling up recycling solutions, both at the national and international levels.

2 DISSEMINATION PROCEDURE

Based on the Grant Agreement of the project, QUASAR data, as well as all project reports and consortium meetings, are by default confidential for their further industrial exploitation. Rules of protection and publication: GA - Chapter 4 / Section 2 - Articles 15 f.

2.1 GENERAL RULE

Any scientific publication or information about emerging protectable results should be put available to the consortium on the project SharePoint 45 days before planned publication.

All the partners have 30 days to disapprove (or approve) the data or partial data envisaged to publish. In the absence of any objection within the 30-day period, it is deemed that the parties agree. If an objection is raised within the 30-day period, the affected parties shall seek in good faith a solution on a timely basis.

2.2 PROCEDURE FOR PARTNERS: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION OR PATENT

In accordance with the Consortium Agreement, any case involving scientific publication or the emergence of protectable results (such as patents, trademarks, or utility models) needs to follow the process as stated below:

For conference abstracts, non-published presentations (ppt), delays are shorter:
21 days prior to the deadline review: 15 days

Step 1: Primary Author send to Dissemination Manager the proposed publications (including mandatory acknowledgement) at least 45 calendar days before the submission (21 days for abstracts and presentations):

- Date of publication and submission, journal name
- Date, title and location of the actual event
- Names and affiliations of all the co-authors
- Any other relevant information

Step 2: Dissemination Manager uploads the draft on the collaborative platform. Any objection shall be made to the Dissemination Manager, Support to Project Management and Primary

Author within 30 calendar days (15 days for abstracts and presentations) after receipt of the publication.

The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raised such an objection. After 90 calendar day, the publication is permitted, provided that Confidential Information of the objecting Party has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting Party.

Step 3: Once reviewed, the primary author submits the final version to the Dissemination Manager

Final version of publications is stored onto the collaborative platform

Final version numbering

Step 4: The Dissemination Manager updates the QUASAR Activity Report and the platform every 6 months

Step 5: The Dissemination Manager informs INEA Communication Officer of any relevant dissemination activities. A list of actual publications will be included in the public website.

Please note that a publication and/or a breach of confidentiality can destroy the protection of an invention.

3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

3.1 RESPONSIBILITY

The project's communication, dissemination and outreach activities are bundled in Work Package 13 and led by The Norwegian Solar Energy Cluster (SEC). It is the Work Package Leader's responsibility to initiate preparation of a communication strategy/plan and to budget for communication activities. Project participants shall contribute with technical input to communication activities, which includes regular updates (progress / results of respective Work Packages; participation at conferences etc.) and at least 5 articles per partner for our website/social media channels. The Project's Coordinator Martin Bellmann (SINTEF) shall assist with user-focused and research communication, as well as quality assurance and/or the preparation of communication plans. The messages shall be used across various platforms and communication channels to raise awareness about the QUASAR project.

3.2 PROJECT NEEDS DEFINITION

The main strategic objectives of the external communication and dissemination plan is to make QUASAR known and to communicate about the project's progress, public results and best practice as far and wide as possible, both within the consortium but also externally.

The communication and dissemination activities shall maximize the promotion of the project and its impact.

The communication strategy aims at the following:

- Foster dialogue and collaboration with relevant target groups, gathering useful feedback from all stakeholders, including researchers, industries, industrial associations, standardization bodies, and other projects.
- Disseminate information by promoting the project and its results, inspiring the industry to adopt targeted outcomes, and promoting novel solar recycling technologies to the public.
- Organize workshops and webinars, integrating them into existing university-level teaching programs on recycling.

Communicating QUASAR's actions and results is an integral part of the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and is essential to maximize the impact of the research, transfer knowledge and results and demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackle societal challenges. However, it is expected that QUASAR will generate data for further industrial exploitation. Therefore, considerable care is required to ensure that the project meets both Horizon Europe's communication activities as well as the necessary protections required to maintain intellectual property rights.

The communication and dissemination measures are expected to streamline project workflows, enhance the outreach of results, and make EOL Decision Support and Recycling Technologies accessible to the broader community and by this facilitating a circular economy for the PV industry.

To achieve this, we need to implement the following communication strategies:

- Build trust and a strong reputation for the project.
- Ensure that information and communication are reliable and coordinated.
- Ensure that information and communication are consistent, unified, with regular frequency, and of good quality.
- Communicate and inform effectively to reach the target audiences.
- Adapt messages to different target groups and channels.
- Contribute to a good internal workflow and knowledge sharing within the project.
- Ensure that the results of communication efforts are measured, and continuously evaluate and improve them.

3.3 STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION

Identifying stakeholders is the process of targeting groups and organizations for QUASAR communication measures. During the first year of the project, stakeholder involvement will be mainly about creating awareness of the project and its value creation. The stakeholders identified by EPRI in Task 13.1 will be targeted through a variety of communication channels and with materials that will suit them best.

The stakeholder inventory will be continuously updated during the project’s lifetime. In previous experience, such stakeholder analysis has proven extremely useful for an adequate, effective and efficient involvement of the wider stakeholder group, both for targeted communication and communication actions, as well as exploitation strategy development.

The communication includes both user-focused and more universal communication. Separate plans should be prepared for researcher-focused communication, in collaboration with the Project Coordinator at SINTEF and the respective Work Package Leaders.

The methodology of communication/dissemination will rely on influence and interest of the stakeholders and each category will have its own communication/dissemination strategy. The following figure will state the most relevant channels. The target groups will determine the most appropriate language(s) and channels.

3.4 PROJECT IDENTITY

The QUASAR visual identity has been defined. This visual identity aims to convey the purpose of the project, its spirit and ambitions and facilitate identification of the project.

Figure: QUASAR project logo

3.5 MAIN COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

To reach the different stakeholder groups, the consortium will rely on different channels. Table 1 presents the targeted audiences for the use of each channel. In addition, all partners will be asked to contribute through their own communication channels, to disseminate project information where relevant.

Table 1 : QUASAR targeted audience for each channel

Channels	Targeted audiences			
	Potential defenders / disseminators	Potential users	Technical and scientific experts	Citizens / students
Online channels				
Website	X	X	X	X
Social media	X	X	X	X
Offline channels				
Conferences, seminars and workshops	X	X	X	
Technical and demonstration workshops	X	X	X	X

Journal publications	X	X	X	X
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3.6 WORK ACTION PLAN AND ROLE OF PARTNERS

The communication and dissemination measures are expected to streamline project workflows, enhance the outreach of results, and make EOL Decision Support and Recycling Technologies accessible to the broader community and by this facilitating a circular economy for the PV industry. This is how we will carry out our communication activities:

3.3.1 Communication and public outreach:

- Website
- Social Media
- Project Video

All partners are committed to generate a stream of new input and to write blogs for the website and targeted social media: (at least) 5 posts in the 4-year project, with the communication planning ensuring good timing for results and relevant spread of posts throughout the project.

SEC will produce project videos to promote the project and improve the awareness of relevant external stakeholders and the general public across the EU. The aim is to produce around 5 short clips of max 2 minutes to be used in the websites blogs and on social media and approximately 3 videos of about 5 minutes length each for targeted audiences.

Partners will share updates on project activities and R&D needs with the interested public through webcasts and published resources (such as short technical briefs highlighting project developments, FAQ sheets, and infographics). In addition, consortium partners will identify suitable content for webcasts and publications and develop a distribution list for communicating with public stakeholders.

3.3.2 Dissemination of materials to stakeholders:

- Brochure / Flyer
- Public version of Waste Management Reports (WP1)
- Monitoring of / participation in relevant European events
- Networking

SEC - with help from the partners - will create a brochure/flyer with information about the project, the challenges it addresses, its potential for future exploitation, and the products and services in development (early project phase). The project brochure will be updated based on information from the Exploitation Manager (BIFA) in M30, to provide stakeholders with an overview on how the project is progressing.

In addition, each Waste Inventory report from WP1 will be made available in a public version to facilitate data transfer to the Raw Materials Information System (RMiS).

All partners will monitor European events that may be relevant for the project as platform to present results, create awareness or initiate a dialogue with decision makers to increase impact,

Participation in these events being discussed in telecons or as part of the updates to the communication plan and communicated through our various channels.

3.3.3 Publications to the scientific and business domain:

- At least 10 publications, either in international journals or through relevant conferences.
- Publication and attendance at European conferences, providing unique interactions with the scientific and business RTD community.

3.3.4 Training and educational resources for EOL service providers and for interested public:

- Developing multiple training methods
- Updates on project activities and R&D needs

In collaboration with other partners, EPRI will define learning goals, design content, and determine effective ways to train EOL services providers. Multiple training methods will be offered, including an in-person 1-day workshop, a webinar series, and development of an online training module (EPRI|U training module = selfpaced, on-demand modules that can incorporate videos, graphics, and knowledge check quizzes to break up training and improve learning).

4 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The online communication tools already set up by SEC.

The project public website has been created, including non-confidential information about the project background and goals. It will regularly be updated with project results and other project related information. The project public website is operational since May 2024 (www.quasar-project.eu). The deliverable D13.1 present with more details the website organization and content.

The QUASAR LinkedIn profile, created by SEC, can be found at the following address: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/QUASAR-easme>. It has been operational since February 2024. The number of followers on LinkedIn will be monitored every six months.

Figure above: QUASAR landing page (www.quasar-project.eu)

Figure: LinkedIn page

4.1 CONFERENCES, SEMINARS AND WORKSHOPS

The dissemination of the QUASAR project will be maximized through regular participation to dedicated conferences and workshops. It is expected that results will be presented at least at 3 international events per year over the entire duration of the project.

- Targeted International Conferences: IRRC Waste to Energy, Intersolar, RE+.
- Targeted European Conferences: EUPVSEC, E-Waste World Conference and Expo, Solar Power Summit,
- Large Scale Solar Europe, Solar & Storage Live.

4.2 TECHNICAL AND DEMONSTRATION WORKSHOPS

QUASAR will organize three workshops during its lifetime.

4.3 JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

QUASAR will follow an open and active publication policy through peer-reviewed in scientific journals. The publications will be made available Open Access by using both the Green and the Golden Route. As for the Green route, the publications will be made available through the institutional repositories of each Partner of the Consortium and on the website of QUASAR. As for the Golden route, the publications will be made available Open Access directly at the Publisher. A publication fee is required in this case (for most of the Publishers) and this will be covered by the Author Institutions. We expect at least 11 scientific publications by the end of the project.

- Publications in Les Echos (French), La Tribune (French), PES magazine (English), EPRI' s Environmental
- Aspects of Solar program (www.epri.com/easolar - English), PV Magazine (English).

5 MONITORING AND EVALUATION PLAN

Communication and dissemination activities will be regularly monitored during the project lifetime to assess the effectiveness of the activities realized and implement changes, if necessary, through:

- Web statistics
- Visibility on social media
- Direct, qualitative enquiries

Communication and dissemination activities will be regularly monitored during the project lifetime to assess the effectiveness of the activities realized and implement changes if necessary.

For this purpose, several Key Performance Indicators (KPI) have been defined with target numbers (Table 4).

Table: WP13 Key Performance Indicators

Dissemination channels	KPI
LinkedIn followers	At least 300 LinkedIn followers by the end of the project, 24 posts per year
Communication / Dissemination activities	At least 10 Communication / Dissemination activities per year
Publications	At least 11 scientific publications in open access in peer-reviewed journals
Website performance	At least 10 000 Views on the website at the end of the project

APPENDIX I - ACTIVITY PLAN

Communication Measure	Description	Date / Frequency	Responsible
Project identity and material	Design of a project identity for consistent use of all partners, including a project logo, presentation templates and other info material (posters, factsheets, flyers) to use at workshops, events and conferences.	M6	SINTEF
Webpage	Setting up a webpage for the project, which will be the project's main dissemination channel and landing page. The webpage will contain project scope and activities, updates and results, logo, relevant links, documents and materials.	M9	SEC
Social media	Enhancing project visibility by actively utilizing the partners social media platforms, such as LinkedIn, LinkedIn etc.	20 posts	WP Leader / Project Manager / All partners
Press releases / news articles / science articles	Promotion of the project and the project's results through press releases, news articles and blog posts on the partners websites, through partners newsletters and tips to media.	Up to 3 articles	All partners
Scientific publications	Publish scientific peer-reviewed, open-access publications and articles in international specialist press, journals, blogs etc.	Up to 3 papers	All partners
Participation at fairs, conferences and events	Present the project and its results at European and international conferences, events, fairs, and congresses. Participation on collaborative events with sister projects.	3 events per year	All partners
Videos	5 short clips of max 2 minutes to be used in the websites blogs & social media and 3 videos of about 5 minutes for targeted audiences.		SEC, SINTEF

APPENDIX II - INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Actions	Message	Target group	Channel	Deadline / frequency	Person(s) responsible
Kick Off	To review project objectives, scope and approach	Project team	Meeting / webinar Minutes of meetings	On start-up	Project Coordinator
Project Meetings	To review project progress, get aligned (information sharing and coordination) and next steps	Project team	Meeting / webinar Minutes of meetings	Ongoing throughout the project period / Every 3-6 months	Project Coordinator
Sharing of work documents	To ensure information sharing, coordination and consultation	Project team	Project room	Ongoing throughout the project period	Project team, partners and suppliers
		Partners	Sharepoint		
		Suppliers			

